

Geometric Distribution and Sieve of Prime Numbers and All Numbers, Exclusively At The -1cone (1:3pythagoras).

The breakup of the Riemann’s hypothesis by prime number distribution at -1 cone: The correct numbers system, as created.

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Abstract: This paper has clearly proven that -1 cone at Pythagoras 1:3 is the absolute **exclusive correct** placement of numbers and prime numbers. This is the brief expose of absolute geometric unravelling of prime numbers at the -1 cone, it is irrefutable mathematics, and as such, “ ipso facto”. The Geometric sieve of the Prime numbers is absolute. The distribution and precise placement of all numbers and prime numbers is mathematically geometric at the half-line, specifically the prime numbers lined at the half-line. The basis for this discovery is related to a published paper from two months ago. The Irrefutable proof of placement of prime numbers at the -1 cone, and rhythm of prime numbers is presented at the end of this paper

Key Words: Prime numbers distribution, Proof of prime number cords, Inverse cone at -1, -1Vedic Zero,1:3 Pythagoras, breakup of the Riemann’s hypothesis.

Signature equation(Katie’s Equation): This mathematics is precisely based on the -1 Vedic zero, at 1:3 Pythagoras which manifest -1 at 5 and6. Readers may solve the equation for *all numbers except X=-1*, it proves a constant span of 6 at 1(sagittal dimension of the cone).

Infinitum in this paper means, “ o fPredictable indefinite mathematical weave”

(The equation discovered is for general equation of a cone at any value of n, but here at -1cone at 1:3 cone, X=3)

Solution to **Katie’s** equation for a Cone progression. In the case of -1 cone (X=3) $Y=v(X^2+1)$

$$X + Y = \frac{1}{X - Y}$$
$$X - Y = \frac{1}{X + Y}$$

By the +1 and -1 of the equation, note 6 at 35.....10.....8

4.....8.....6

3.....6.....4

2.....4.....2

1.....2.....0

At the Katie's equation $\sqrt{(3^2+1)*6}=\sqrt{(19^2-1)}=\sqrt{360}$

Configuration: $\sqrt{2}/(\sqrt{10}-\sqrt{8})=2+\sqrt{5}$ plus infinitum of these configurations

Basic mathematics in this thesis, which is part 2 of a published paper, is by geometric position at the 1:3 cone. Geometric positioning by numbers must have a common mathematical factor to both. That common factor is 1:3, throughout this thesis as well as the finite universe. The sphere collapses to a 1:3 cone, and the cone expands to a sphere.

PROOF 1: Diagram of the one standard Constant of non-linear space and Pythagoras at 1:3,-1 unknown to Mathematics in its history, by its relevance.

Constant 5 and 6: non-linear space
By the grace of my Lord Jesus Christ

The span here is 6 constant(3+3), height is 1 and the radii is -1 at 5. This is the manifestation of -1 at 5,6.

$1/6+5/6=1$, is an expression of -1 at value 6. The novel exclusive discovery of the Penta-1, 1:6 fixed curved space constant for all numbers: This is also proof of Pythagoras 1:3 in non-linear space as the curve represents the configuration of Pythagoras 1:3 as a cone at the apex of the diagram at -1 (the height of 1) at the curve is the basis of the 1:3 cone)

$N/6 = \text{residua } 1/6$ $N/6 = \text{residua } 5/6$

At the apex of the diagram centered by upright of 1 is the 1:3 cone expansion.

At 6 span the radius is 5 and the height is 1. This is a 1:6 constant built into the geometry (height =1). This basically is a constant in space as described earlier in the published paper. No other numbers do that.

1:3 cone (distribution of prime numbers and numbers) Please reference this diagram with the Pre-Calculus that follows,

Note on the cone diagram: All numbers are at + 3 half-line on a -1 cone, all placement is at the half-line of 1:3, cone -1. *The -1 cone at Pythagoras 1:3, and the angle of genesis from Infinity are fully discussed in the published part 1 of this paper as referenced below.* The 1:3 Cone is a Geometric form, and this is unique to 3 and 4. The upright numbers are continuum with the half line number.

3(1) 4...3,4

6(2) 8...6,7,8

9(3) 12...9,10,11,12

This differential with numbers continuum and geometry, which is by whole numbers is a mathematical fact that has been explained in the previous paper referenced below. At value 3 and 4 is the base of that differential. Whole numbers continuum is not rational with geometric form and at 1:3 Pythagoras that is 3:4 (sphere vs square). It is beyond the scope of this paper to explain to mathematicians, the mathematical logic further. It should be noted that even with regard to Fermat's Theorem, that simply $5^3+6^3=7^3-2$ is the least after $3^2+4^2=5^2-0$, for all values and that no numbers can break that rule, that's a simple proof of Fermat's. Note the rather complex solution to a simple theorem is a complex one (in Science things are simpler before they are complex.) To every complexity, there is a simple answer at the base of mathematics continuum. (Sure! Complexity is more impressive and wins acclaim, but that's not the way it is with the precise mathematics).

$$3^2+4^2=5^2-0$$

$$5^3+6^3=7^3-2$$

1.GEOMETRIC SIEVE OF THE HALF-LINE OF THE CONE- MATRIX, INFINITUM:

1A.

Show case window for mathematicians, the calculus follows:

Mathematicians may never understand this unorthodox calculus without a “show case”, as this is very complex without a show case. Please take it slow as there is prejudice against unorthodoxy in current mathematics which the author has experienced. A show case window is presented to make the mathematicians of the world understand this mathematical resolution. There are three basic arrangements at the linear half-line at +3

The +3 series at the half-line of the -1 cone (+3,6,9,12,15,18,21...) +3 and 1[^] value up in the geometric cone at 1:3 Pythagoras, has three series besides the fixed half-line at +3,

The first series is of all numbers divisible /9 (9,18,27,36...)

The second series at the half line is numbers divisible by /6 , (6,12,18,24)

The third series at the half- line is comprised of prime numbers and pseudo prime numbers derivatives (15,21,33,39,) but not the /6 or /9 and the rhythm of the series is every 6 and 12 numeration, in two cords on each side of the half-line.

The numbers at the half line that are not /6 or/ 9 series are made up of prime numbers and all divisible numbers. These are placed at 6,12, 6,12, 6,12....by geometric format. These are as follows,

15,21.....,33,3951,57,..... 69,75.....87, 93...105,111...

..

15+6=21 ,33+6=39 ,51+6=57, 69+6=75 ,87+6=93

$21+12=33, 39+12=51, 57+12=69, 93+12=105,$

Starting at the first few numbers of the series that are not divisible i.e. 5,7,11,13, that process progresses and sieves for the next batch of prime numbers that advance the sieve process. At **7(21)**: The placement gaps are $(6*7=42),(7*12=84)\dots 42, 84, 42,84,\dots$ (6,12 recurrent)

At **11(33)**:The placement gaps are $(6*11=66),(12*11=132)$ (66,132...66,132..) (6,12 6,12 recurrent)

At **13(39)**:The placement gaps are, 78,156 ... 78,156.. (6,12...6,12 recurrent)

At **17(51)** The placement gaps are, 102,204 ...102,204... 102,204...102,204 (6,12 6,12 recurrent)

At **19(57)**: The placement gaps are 114, 228,... 114 228, ... (6,12 6,12 recurrent)

Infinite geometric elimination of Pseudo-prime numbers marked by this example of these 4 base prime numbers X3 each i.e. 21,33,39,51,57... You start with a few and then automatically you build up a list of non- divisible numbers by geometric position, that is used to find more and more divisible numbers generating pseudo prime numbers by position and geometry of the cone. This marks the exact position of the prime and Pseudo prime at the +3 half-line.

1B.

ELIMINATION OF DIVISIBLE NUMBERS BY GEOMETRIC PLACEMENT AT THE CONE:

The object is to mark position of each value sieved, relative to a cone progression. See method of the inordinate numbers after this show case. Unknown numbers even like 15, 21, 33 ,39 ,51,57... etc. all start from the generated list in blue below. starter value is 15 for all numbers. Descending order of the divisible numbers all add up to the progression of the geometric sieve , starting from the first 3-4 prime numbers and all further sieved prime numbers add progressively to the sieved matrix .all divisible by three/or5(342) are ignored by the segregated series, The calculus below is shown above as a 6,12 format which is the format of this third series. It starts with 5 prime numbers and then progresses to all the cone matrix as is shown below and any mind can figure it out.

21(7) (42:84)	33(11)(66:132)	39(13)(78:156)	51(17)(102:204)	57(19)(114:228)
$21+84=105/3=15$	$33+132=165/11=15$	$39+156=195/13=15$	$51+204=255/17=15$	$57+228=285/19=15$
$105+42=147.$	$165+66=231.$	$195+78=273.$	$255+102=357.$	$285+114=399.$
$147+84=231.$	$231+132=363.$	$273+156=429.$	$357+204=561.$	$399+228=627.$
$231+42= 273.$	$363+66=429.$	$429+78 =507.$	$561+102=663.$	$627+114=741.$
$273+84=357.$	$429+132=561.$	$507+156=663.$	$663+204=867.$	$741+228=969.$
$357+42=399.$	$561+66=627.$	$663+78=741.$	$867+102=969.$	$969+114=1083$
$399+84= 483.$	$627+132=759.$	$741+156=897.$	$969+204=1173$	$1083+228=1211$
$483+42=525.$	$759+66=825$	$897+78=975$	$1173+102=1377$	$1211+114=1325$
$525+84=609.$	$825+132=957$	$975+156=1131$	$1377+204=1581$	$1325+228=1553$
$609+42=651$	$957+66=1023$	$1131+78=1209$	$1581+102=1683$	$1553+114=1667$

The following inordinate series of numbers not divisible by 6 or 9, is sieved in blue numbers which numbers then cancel out non- prime numbers extrapolated above. Please it is that simple

9	+ 6	15	(5)/(3)
9	+12	21	(7)
18	+15	33	(11)
18	+21	39	(13)
18	+33	51	(17)
18	+39	57	(19)
18	+51	69	(23)
18	+57	75	(25)
18	+69	87	(29)
18	+75	93	(31)
18	+87	105	(35)
18	+93	111	(37)
18	+105	123	(41)
18	+111	129	(43)
18	+123	141	(47)
18	+129	147	(49)***
18	+141	159	(53)
18	+147	165	(55)
18	+159	177	(59)
18	+165	183	(61)
18	+177	195	(65)

18	+183	201	(67)
18	+195	213	(71)
18	+201	219	(73)
18	+213	231	(77)**
18	+219	237	(79)
18	+231	249	(83)
18	+237	255	(85)
18	+249	267	(89)
18	+255	273	(91)**
18	+267	285	(95)
18	+273	291	(97)
18	+285	303	(101)
18	+291	309	(103)

18	+303	321	(107)
18	+309	327	(109)
18	+321	339	(113)
18	+327	345	(115)
18	+339	357	(119)***
18	+345	363	(121)***
18	+357	375	(125)
18	+363	381	(127)
18	+375	393	(131)
18	+381	399	(133)***
18	+393	411	(137)
18	+399	417	(139)
18	+411	429	(143)***
18	+417	435	(145)
18	+429	447	(149)
18	+435	453	(151)
18	+447	465	(153)
18	+453	471	(157)
18	+465	483	(161)***
18	+471	489	(163)
18	+483	501	(167)
18	+489	507	(169)** *
18	+501	519	(173)
18	+507	525	(175)
18	+519	537	(179)
18	+525	543	(181)
18	+537	555	(185)
18	+543	561	(187)***
18	+555	573	(191)
18	+561	579	(193)
18	+573	591	(197)
18	+579	597	(199)
18	+591	609	(203)***

18	+597	615	(205)
18	+609	627	(209)***
18	+615	633	(211)

18	+627	645	(215)
18	+633	651	(217)***
18	+645	663	(221)***
18	+651	669	(223)
18	+663	681	(227)
18	+669	687	(229)
18	+681	699	(233)
18	+687	705	(235)
18	+699	717	(230)
18	+705	723	(241)
18	+717	735	(245)
18	+723	741	(247)***
18	+735	753	(251)
18	+741	759	(253)***
18	+753	771	(257)
18	+759	777	(259)
18	+771	789	(263)
18	+777	795	(365)
18	+789	807	(269)
18	+795	813	(271)
18	+807	825	(275)
18	+813	831	(277)
18	+825	843	(281)
18	+831	849	(283)
18	+843	861	(287)
18	+849	867	(289)***
18	+861	879	(293)
18	+867	885	(295)
18	+879	897	(299)***
18	+885	903	(301)
18	+897	915	(305)
18	+903	921	(307)
18	+915	933	(311)
18	+921	939	(313)
18	+933	951	(317)
18	+939	957	(319)***
18	+951	969	(323)***
18	+957	975	(325)

18	+969	987	(329)
18	+975	993	(331)
18	+987	1005	(333)
18	+993	1011	(337)
18	+1005	1023	(341)***
18	+1011	1029	(343)
18	+1023	1041	(347)
18	+1029	1047	(349)

The series above is derived by simple calculus. In the right column the series numbers are “infitum” and constant and basically they are arranged as two cords at the half-line, basically as +6,+12 as shown above . At the half-line this series is arranged hugging the half-line as to cords with each having distinctive features follows in the first row below as taken from the sieve above, this series is infitum(indefinite)

15...21..33...39..51...57...75..87...93..105..111...123.....
(5....7....11...13..17.19...25..29...31...35...37.....41)...../3

The half- line numbers when /6 have a constant residua of1/6 , and the second row numbers when divided by /6 have a residua of 5/6

5, 8, 11, 14, 17, 20, 23, 26, 29, 32, 35, 38, 41,44.... cord2
4, 7, 10, 13, 16, 19, 22, 25, 28, 31, 34, 37,40,43.... cord1
3, 6, 9, 12 15 18 21 24 27 30 33 36 39 42--- the half line of the cone

1.C.

PRE-CALCULUS FOR NUMBERS PLACEMENT:

These starter prime numbers are first displayed by their placement and rhythm, first to restate the three series that comprise the half-line

- A. One series is at /+9 over the +3 at the half line (9,18,27,36,45),
- B. The second series is ordinate at/ +6 over + 3 half- line (6,12,18,24,30,36,42..) at Pythagoras 1:3, which role is infinite in a finite series.
- C. The third series on which **all prime** numbers and pseudo prime numbers ride , is the series at + 3 half-line that is neither at/9 and /6 , but runs at numbers that are X3 of prime numbers an d runs at 6, 12 ; 6:12 6.12.....as15,21,33,39,51 ...

The complicated mosaic of numbers at Pythagoras 1:3 that appear to be a jumble but are rational as shown at Pythagoras 1:3, -1. Besides the three series, there are ordinate gaps of numbers based on the half-line called rhythm of a prime number as shown further below

1.D(for counting, separate issue to placement)

3,6,9,12,15,18,21,24,27,30,21...half line +3....is the linear half line at Pythagoras 1:3 cone with two columns of prime numbers as in the published paper.

1.E.

4,8,12,16,20,24,28,32 upright at the hypotenuse.... These are the numbers line at the hypotenuse of the Pythagoras 1:3 at the upright. $9/3=3$, so the upright numbers are $9+3=12$; likewise at 21, $21/3=7$, 7 ,numbers are $21+7=28$, 28 being at the hypotenuse /upright of the Pythagoras 1:3.

1.F

5,10,15,20,25,30,35 the5:6 configuration prime 5... based on the prime number 5 at the configuration at 5,6 as shown in the original published paper and the cone diagram above, as such it is,

3:5 ;6:10; 9:15,12:20 This is critical and configures Pythagoras 1:3 and 1:2.

These basic number arrangements are based on geometry and related by the values of +9 and +6 and the series not at +9 or +6 at the half-line (that inordinate series is cross marked exclusively by prime number 19 and all other subsequent prime numbers.)

Caution: These three are the reference series . These values below are critical for the numbers series, very precise. highlighted yellow are numbers that do not belong to either+ 9 or +6 series, i.e. inordinate series that contain all prime numbers and pseudo prime numbers.

3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45
4	8	12	16	20	24	28	32	36	40	44	48	52	56	60
5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75

2.0

GEOMETRIC PLACEMENT AND FUNCTION OF ALL NUMBER SYSTEM INCLUDING PRIME NUMBERS , AT THE -1 CONE

Arrangement table of the two cords hugging the half line and indefinite twin Prime number arrangement at the two cords, since the half-line is fixed and both cords advance by a fixed. +6. The blue and red cords in the table are the two cords at the half-line, the cord prime numbers at the half-line that are /6 leave a residue of 1/6 , whilst the cord numbers in the second row at the half-line that are /6 yield a residue of 5/6. The arrangement of these half-line numbers when they are converted to X3 is rational and ordinate at 6, 12 6,12, 6,12.....infinitem

15,21,33,39,51,57,69,75,87,93,105 ,111, 123,129, 141,147.....infinitem at 6,12 6,12 6,12 also shown at the table above are exactly the same numbers as at the half-line base. But the fact is that these very numbers that hug the half line are well set and organized basically In the 6, 12 6,12 6,12.....rhythm, infinitem. This very series have been geometrically Sieved in Part 1

This cone numbers system is NOT the man made linear number system and or its many novelties that are out there in the mathematical world as the current numbers theory of sorts , this is the number system of a Cone and a perfect sphere in which exclusively the prime numbers are arranged at the half-

line by infinite calculus as shown and the Prime numbers and value 10 act as cross markers infinitum and mark the position of every number and prime number in the cone matrix infinitum. Please note the following caveats. Also note that in this cone matrix of prime numbers and all numbers at the half-line are +3 and on the outer edge of the cone these are +4

2A.

Understanding the correct number system:

Cone matrix numbers continuum and cross marking of all numbers.

Unique rhythm of the Prime numbers.

Functionality of prime numbers in the cone matrix.

Cone matrix numbers expand at the cone from the half-line, they fan out. The rhythm of the Prime numbers is unique, it is rational, constant and infinitum. It basically means that the position of the Prime number is fixed vertically relative to the half-line as well as cross marking multiples of the prime number infinitum, with the count of numbers above and below the multiple. **So it is apparent that the position of all functional prime numbers** are fixed at the half line, and the position of its multiples throughout the cone matrix are fixed by the rational unique rhythm and placement of the prime numbers and its multiples of the Prime number, which in the case of Prime numbers is infinitum. This value is rational as follows,

Step up/ cross mark slope at 47 :;47+47+47+47+47+47+47

Step up/cross mark slope at 49:: 49+49+49+40+49+49+49+49 (49 step divides along the cross mark by 7, 14,21,28 so on hardly their mark of a virgin number

Prime numbers have this perfect rhythm and also their cross marking is stable infinitum, not so other non-prime numbers. The following prime numbers place their multiples infinitum in the following order, starting at the half-line." Placement cross marking"rhythm is separate

Placement rhythm at the half-line.

11 every+9, infinitum
13 every+12, infinitum
17 every +15, infinitum
19 every +18, infinitum
23 every+18, infinitum(reverse. top down)
29 every +27, infinitum
31 every +30, infinitum

Cross marking rhythm table shown below, for individual prime numbers .

Progression code it the top number and the bottom number at progressive multiples of the prime numbers.

2B.

Rhythm of Prime 7 and code=

1 ,2 ,3 ,4 .. up^ to hypotenuse at successive numbers , Progression code (6:8)(12,16)(18:24)....>

1 ,2 ,3 ,4.. bottom down to the half-line at successive numbers

Rhythm of Prime number **11** and code =

1 ,2 ,3 ,4 ,5 ,6.. up^ to the hypotenuse, at progression code (9:12),(18:24)(27:36)....>

2 ,4 ,6 ,8 ,10 bottom ,down to the half-line

Rhythm of prime number 13 and code=

3 ,6 ,9 ,12 ..up to the hypotenuse. Progression code(12:16),(24,32),(36,48).....>

1 ,2 ,3 ,4 bottom down to the half-line

Rhythm of Prime number **19** and code=

5 ,10 ,15 ,20..up^ to the hypotenuse. Progression code(18:24),(36.48),36:49).....>

1 ,2 ,3 ,4 down to the Half- line

So on for all Prime numbers,

2C.

TABLES FOR SPECIFIC PRIME NUMBER RHYTHM AND PROGRESSION CODE

The Specific Role of Prime numbers is as marker divisors of the cone numbers matrix infinitum and their placement at the half line creates a rhythm of each prime number, as shown .These primary marker prime numbers shown are 7, 11,13 19,23,but all Prime numbers and the value 10 cross mark the **numbers** matrix infinitum in the composite cone matrix as shown **always in the same tangent linear frame, constant rhythm, unlike the divisible numbers** . All numbers and prime numbers infinitum divide the -1 cone matrix of numbers . These are shown separately

The **divisible numbers do not** cross -mark the matrix infinitum, only prime numbers do that the natural arrangement of numbers.

To mark the divisor number placement count the numbers slots from the half-line up are constant as it progresses in predictable manner, perfectly. For instance, if you want to mark the position to the half line at **19 *1000** mark you can predict the exact mark down count to the half line and then the prime numbers at that marked placement

Placement of prime numbers by the half line demonstrates the **two cords** that have been shown in the published paper and confirmed by the quadratic Algebra, a short example is shown in the text . **There is a purpose for this (rotation)** and the author has a new quadratic algebra to prove these two cords. The precise purpose is that they regulate the base distance from the half line in the cross marking as follows,

5,11,17, 23,31.....

7,13,19, 29,37

The Quadratic algebra is demonstrated below.

2D.

TABLES FOR SPECIFIC PRIME NUMBER RHYTHM AND PROGRESSION CODE

The oscillating role and function of the Prime number placement and rhythm and the cross marking of the numbers matrix is explained by the simple observation that these “steps to a slope” of a cone have to be numbered are a non – divisible step with each step being +19 or +17, or +101 infinitum, these steps define the slope of the cone. Each prime number has a unique rhythm t climb

(Duplicate):Prime numbers have this perfect rhythm and also their cross making is stable infinitum , not so other non-prime numbers .The following prime numbers place their multiples infinitum in the following order, starting at the half- line. Placement cross marking rhythm is separate and explained.

Placement rhythm at the half-line only, by the two fixed cord arrangement which is deducible

- 11 every +9 , infinitum
- 13 every+12, infinitum
- 17 every +15, infinitum
- 19 every +18,infinitum
- 23 every+21,infinitum(reverse. top down)
- 29 every +27, infinitum
- 31 every+30, infinitum
- 37 every +36,infinitum
- 41 every +39 infinitum

Cross marking rhythm table shown below .

Rhythm of Prime 7 and code=

1 ,2 ,3 ,4 .. up to hypotenuse at successive numbers , progression code (6:8)(12,16)(18:24)....>

1 ,2 ,3 ,4.. bottom down to the half-line at successive numbers

Rhythm of Prime number 11 and code =

1 ,2 ,3 ,4 ,5 ,6.. up to the hypotenuse, at progression code (9:12),(18:24)(27:36)....>

2 ,4 ,6 ,8,10bottom ,down to the half-line

Rhythm of prime number 13 and code=

3 , 6 ,9 ,12 ..up to the hypotenuse. Progression code(12:16),(24,32),(36,48).....>

1 , 2 ,3 ,4 bottom down to the half-line

Rhythm of prime number17 and code=

3,6,9,12... up to the hypotenuse, progression code (15:20),(30:40)(45:60)

2,4,6,8... down to the half-line

Rhythm of Prime number 19 and code=

Table at every +6,12,18,24, prime 7 and 13 cross mark the cone matrix infinitum

						56	62							
						55	61							
					48	54	60							
					47	53	59							
				40	46	52	58							
				39	45	51	57							
			32	38	44	50	56							
			31	37	43	49	55							
		24	30	36	42	48	54							
		23	29	35	41	47	53							
	16	22	28	34	40	46	52*							
	15	21	27	33	39*	45	51							
8	14	20	26*	32	38	44	50							
7	13*	19	25	31	37	43	49							
6	12	18	24	30	36	42	48							

2F.

Composite Prime number Cone matrix table, marker Prime numbers 7, 11, 19 as examples shown here in two sets for space, but all Prime numbers cross mark infinitum. Note that the two cords of prime number in two separate cords (by rhythm) hugging the half-line, these two cords are predictable by their position, as shown below.

Cone placement of the entire numbers matrix above with the second table showing the next half .The cross marker Prime numbers are counted from the half line(base) and **the first position they appear in the cone matrix**. These cross- markers of prime numbers are infinitum in their marking and have different differentials of counting from the half-line(base),(**rhythm of a prime number**)

2G.

Derivation of Precise placement of the Prime numbers at the half – line :

These are the numbers at +3 half-line, **not** divisible by 6 or 9 already demonstrated above in section 2. These match the half-line numbers exactly as follows, after sieve. These are arranged in two natural cord, as shown below.

1.Raw series which is not sieved for Prime numbers nor arranged in two cords but this is easily done as shown above by method

15,21,33,39,51,57,69,75,87,93,105,111,123,129,141,147,159.165,177

2.Natural segregation of above raw series at +6 ,+12: arranged in two cords hugging the half-line.

15,21,33,39,51,57,69,75,87,93 ,105 ,111, 123,129, 141,147,159 ,165 ,177 ,183

3.Placement of prime numbers hugging at half-line in two cords (: geometrically) . These two cords numbers have a 6 differential each between the corresponding numbers of the two cords and 18 differential collaterally between the numbers of each cord

21,39,57,75,93,111,129,147,165,183

15,33,51,69,87,105,123,141,159,177.

4.Divide each by 3 and these values are precisely the values at the two cords hugging the half-line with a natural differential of 2 each between the corresponding numbers of the two cords and 6 differential collaterally between the two numbers of each cord

7,13,19,25,31,37,43,49,55,61,67,73,79,85,91,97,103,109,115,121,127,133,139,145,151,157,163

5,11,17,23,29,35,41,47,53,59 ,65,71,77,83,89,95,101,107,113,119,125,131,137,143,149,155,161

Note that the series cords numbers have a constant differential of 2 between the two cord numbers

5. Sieve for Prime numbers as shown in Section 2. Final numbers for the half-line , exact match by two cords of the natural lay

7,13,19,31,37,43,61,67,73,79,97, 103...

5,11,17,23,29,41,47,53,59,71,83,89,101

The above is the mathematical sequence of discovery and the ligand proof further validated below by ligand proof, leaving no doubt that prime number are a tight fit for -1 cone .

Composite Cone Matrix table, demonstration of Prime number rhythm from the half-line, 3,6,9...

																			84	87	
																			80	83	86
																	76	79	82	85	
																72	75	78	81	84	
															68	71	74	77	80	83	
														64	67	70	73	76	79	82	
													60	63	66	69	72	75	78	81	
												56	59	62	65	68	71	74	77	80	
											52	55	58	61	64	67	70	73	76	79	
										48	51	54	57	60	63	66	69	72	75	78	
									44	47	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	74	77	
								40	43	46	49	52	55	58	61	64	67	70	73	76	
							36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60	63	66	69	72	75	
						32	35	38	41	44	47	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	74	
					28	31	34	37	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	61	64	67	70	73	
				24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60	63	66	69	72	
			20	23	26	29	32	35	38	41	44	47	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	
		16	19	22	25	28	31	34	37	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	61	64	67	70	
	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60	63	66	69	
8	11	14	17	20	23	26	29	32	35	38	41	44	47	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	

7	10	13	16	19	22	25	28	31	34	37	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	61	64	67
6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60	63	66

									128
								124	127	130	133	136	139	142	145	149	151			
							120	123	126	129	132	135	138	141	144	147	150			
						116	119	122	125	128	131	134	137	140	143	146	149			
					112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	136	139	142	145	148			
				108	111	114	117	120	123	126	129	132	135	138	141	144	147			
			104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134	137	140	143	146			
		100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	136	139	142	145			
	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123	126	129	132	135	140	141	144			
92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134	139	140	143			
91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	136	139	142			
90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123	126	129	132	135	138	141			
89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134	137	140			
88	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	136	139			
87	90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123	126	129	132	135	138			
86	89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134	137			
85	88	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	136			
84	87	90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123	126	129	132	135			
83	86	89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131	134			
82	85	88	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	133			
81	84	87	90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123	126	129	132			
80	83	86	89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128	131			
79	82	85	88	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130			
78	81	84	87	90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123	126	129			
77	80	83	86	89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125	128			
76	79	82	85	88	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127			
75	78	81	84	87	90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123	126			
74	77	80	83	86	89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	125			
73	76	79	82	85	88	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124			
72	75	78	81	84	87	90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120	123			
71	74	77	80	83	86	89	92	95	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122			
70	73	76	79	82	85	88	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121			
69	72	75	78	81	84	87	90	93	96	99	102	105	108	111	114	117	120			

3.0

Arrangement and distribution of all prime numbers at the half-line (hugging the half-line) lower cord numbers $/6=1/6$ residua and closest to the half-line, and the upper cord are numbers $/6$ that leave a $5/6$ residua .These numbers arrangement is infinitum because the half- line is fixed at +3 BUT Note these fact that these numbers before they are converted to division by three they are placed the half-line after sieve 6,12 6,12, 6,12 infinitum ,as follows and as discussed also in the precalculus.

15,21,33,39,51,57,69,75,87,93,105 ,111, 123,129.....infinitum at 6,12 6,12 6,12 also shown at the table below. But the fact is that numbers that hug the half line are well set and organized basically In the numbers series that is not divisible by 6 or 9 and have the placement rhythm +6, +12 + 6,+12 + 6,+12.....rhythm is infinitum.

4.0

IRREFUTABLE PROOF OF PLACEMENT OF PRIME NUMBERS AT THE HALF- LINE OF AN INVERSE-1 CONE THAT EXPANDS INTO A SPHERE.

Proof of sphere/Cone relationship in the referenced published paper, The expansion of the cone matrix numbers is an inverse relationship inverse of a sphere $360/19*19=360$ and the $\sqrt{(10)*6}=v(360)$.

The main function of prime numbers is to cross- mark the cone matrix of numbers by their oscillation and rhythm at the half-line and in so doing provide marking the steps of a slope of the cone matrix non-divisible as +P,+P,+P. This is the proof by ligand binding at the half-line of the cone and its slope that prime numbers are perfect fit at the cone , its half-line and its slope .The half- line runs at +3 and by rhythm 6,1...6,12... 6,12... and the prime numbers oscillate at the half-line by their position .

For a proof by the cone- matrix, I have to prove perfect binding of values that are in cone progression. We must not forget that this is inverse cone placement although numbers placement at the full sphere would be of the same mathematics but in several planes but the following curved equation as described in the previous published paper puts the prime numbers in a spherical perspective.

$$\left[\frac{19^2 - 1}{19} \right] * 19 = 360$$

Now focusing on the proof at the half-line , here is one example

The example of the number 19 at the half-line is used here.

This Proof is by Mathematical ligand (binding of values by a knot in a weave) . This binding is between the Half-line Oscillations. The two cords that hug the half-line) that are divisible by 3

and the corresponding values at the slope/hypotenuse of the cone, these values are divisible by 4.

At Value 18 at the Half line 19 falls at the closest prime number cord hugging the half-line . The height at the slope of the cone is $18/3=6$, $18+6=24$

24

23

22

21

20

19

15... **18**....21

The value at 19 is $24-19=5$

The rest of the values at the half- line, sieve is done before by example, this is simply the proof that the prime number shoe fits the -1cone. I find most mathematicians to be too arrogant but the citadel of current mathematics must and will fall at the hands of this inspired mathematics of the model of the universe black holes etc. **Science is simple first before it is complex.**

5.0. THE PROOF BY “LIGAND” THAT PRIME NUMBERS PLACEMENT ARE SPECIFIC TO 1:3 CONE.(THE DUCKS LINE UP)

The proof by placement at the half line by ligand mathematics: That -1 cone is correct and exclusive placement of prime numbers

Red=ordinate series, 6,12 6,12...series at the half-line , sieved above to remove divisible. The red numbers are not divisible by 6,9 .The half-line series is to the extreme left

Half-line	Cord1	Cord 2			Hypotenuse				ligand		
6	7	8			8		8	-7	=1		
9	10	11			12		12	-11	=1		
12	13	14			16		16	-13	=3		
15	16	17			20		20	-17	=3		
18	19	20			24		24	-19	=5		
21	22	23			28		28	-23	=5		
24	25	26			32		32	-25	=7		
27	28	29			36		36	-29	=7		
30	31	32			40		40	-31	=9		
33	34	35			44		44	-35	=9		
36	37	38			48		48	-37	=11		
39	40	41			52		52	-41	=11		
42	43	44			56		56	-43	=13		
45	47	48			60		60	-47	=13		
48	49	50			64		64	-49	=15		

51	52	53			68		68	-53	=15		
54	55	56			72		72	-55	=17		
57	58	59			76		76	-59	=17		
60	61	63			80		80	-61	=19		
63	64	65			84		84	-65	=19		
66	67	68			88		88	-67	=21		
69	70	71			92		92	-71	=21		
72	73	74			96		96	-73	=23		
75	76	77			100		100	-77	=23		
78	79	80			104		104	-79	=25		
81	82	83			108		108	-83	=25		
84	85	86			112		112	-85	=27		
87	88	89			116		116	-89	=27		
90	91	92			120		120	-91	=29		
93	94	95			124		124	-95	=29		
96	97	98			128		128	-97	=31		
99	100	101			132		132	101	=31		

PROOF 5A:

The dual marker cords of prime number discussed extensively in the published paper, Spiral rotation of the Mathematical cone: This is a very difficult mathematics, it involves Polarity switch.

These cords also hug the half -line and have a spiral role which is much beyond this distribution. These are shown above. This is the breakdown of the quadratic algebra calculus

5,11,17,23,31 ,,,,,

7,13,19,29,37EXAMPLE Set17,23, (XX) (The quadratic Algebra solves this, it was discovered first in our published paper,as to how with quadratic algebra we connect prime numbers of each cord, like prime number 23 to 31, mathematically, this is shown here briefly, the calculus. This calculus is very difficult as current mathematics has not a clue, one example is shown here from the published paper.

The basic calculus of quadratic algebra and of the dual prime number cords and the published quadratic algebra delineating the two cords of prime number in the published paper: This is in the form of clear mathematics verifying the calculation of the values of X ,Y in the quadratic cage as shown I the paper. X and Y rotate by polarity placement from prime number set to set, just as prime numbers oscillate across the half-line. The following is the template solution as an example for all sets, and shows the method of calculating X, Y.

Set, 17,23, (31 unknown).

Carry over is 11 from previous set

17, 23, (XX)

The set value $23+(23-17) = 29$.

$11+18=29$

$X + Y =29$

$23+6 =29$

The value of X and Y solves this by the final quadratic cage at each equation, note the 1:3 (6/18),so called ligand which is in all the equations

The calculation of X and Y ($29*2-18=40$) from above quadratic values,

$[(11*3)-X =18] +[(18*3)-Y] =40.... 40+18=58 (29*2) (15) = X ,(14)=Y$ is specific to the quadratic cage that solves the unknown predicted value as shown below.

The unknown quadratic cage coordinates for the set:

$$8 + 15 =23$$

$$9 + 14 =23$$

.....

$$17 + 29 = 46 , \text{ known coordinates}$$

14 solves the quadratic settings by the span. Next number at the set is 31

$$17+14=31$$

$$23-8+15$$

$$23+8=31$$

Carry over value=**15**. This quadratic Algebra is too complex and will need a separate paper

RESULTS:

These numbers are as they are, as demonstrated precisely. All prime numbers can be geometrically placed, sieved at a half-line of +3 numbers. There is no variance to discuss in this presentation, but discoveries like this and exclusively all numbers of the inordinate numbers at the half-line are understandable as Prime number 19 plays a vital role at the 0-1 cone, as shown in the text of 2 papers. The use of ligand mathematics to prove correct placement at the -1 cone is unique, so is the signature Katie's equation, as is the prime rhythms.

Conclusion:

This is precise complete Placement of Prime numbers and prime numbers, based on two papers, this one and the -1 cone. The resolution of numbers is perfect this is the only rational number series that is rational with Geometry. All numbers are correctly placed and the prime number markers are infinite and hold numbers together. All numbers can be placed and predicted at an expanding cone, that fact is very obvious to a reasonable mathematical mind.

Message to Current Mathematics: Please review your age old theories and adopt a perfectly created mathematics for the future of this world. Mysteries like the "travelling Salesman", are easily resolved. The advent of the linear computer has serious limitations because it has no natural planes of its own and dimensions have to be created. All this will be discussed in the forthcoming book on the work of Isaac Newton and Albert Einstein.

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